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A REVIEW OF PROTEIN EXTRACTED FROM OKARA (SOYBEAN RESIDUE)

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Abstract

Okara, also called soybean residue (SBR), is produced by manufacturing soy products such as soy milk. A large amount of okara is made yearly with low utilisation and added value due to its rough taste and susceptibility to spoilage. Okara can be a good source of low-priced plant protein in the application of human food and animal feeds. There is a need for efficient methods to extract this valuable protein from the okara waste product. It is also necessary to clarify the okara's composition and its protein components, particularly the amino acid profile. Hence, this review provided an update on the protein extraction from okara and the pretreatment methodologies that increase the extraction efficiency process.

Keywords: Okara protein, Extraction, Pretreatment, Homogeniastion, Functionalities.

Introduction

Okara is a waste product created during the process of making soymilk or tofu from soybeans. It contains 50-60% dietary fibre, 20-30% protein, 10-20% lipids, and 70-80% water. There are two varieties of okara: high-fatted and defatted. Annual production is estimated to be 1.4 billion tonnes worldwide, with a significant portion coming from Asian nations. Okara is a soybean residue, bean curd residue, or dreg. It is whitish-yellow in colour and is rich in dietary fibre, unsaturated lipids, high-quality protein, minerals, oligosaccharides, isoflavones, and other compounds. It contains a significant amount of protein (15.2-33.4%), lipid (10%), and fat (about 10%). It also contains a small amount of sugar, such as arabinose, glucose, galactose, fructose, stachyose + raffinose, sucrose, and 0.5% starch.

Okara contains a variety of vitamins and minerals as well. The following mineral compositions are found in 100 g of dry matter of okara: K (1046-1233 mg), Na (16.2-19.1), Ca (260-428 mg), Mg (158-165 mg), Fe (6.0-8.2 mg), Cu (1.1-1.2 mg), Mn (2.2-3.1 mg), Zn (3.5-6.4 mg), P (396-444 mg), Thiamin (0.48-0.59 mg), Riboflavin (0.003-0.004 mg), and Nicotinic acid (0.82-1.04 mg) as reported by Li *et al.* (2008). The following components were reported to be present in 100 g of dry-weight okara by Mateos-Aparicio *et al.* (2010) and Li *et al.* (2012): K (350 mg), Na (30 mg), Ca (320 mg), Mg (130 mg), Fe (0.6 mg), Cu (0.1 mg), Mn (0.2 mg), and Zn (0.3 mg). The mineral compositions of 100 g of okara, according to Wang *et al.* (2010), are as follows: K (936 mg), Na (96 mg), Ca (419 mg), Mg (257 mg), Fe (11 mg), Cu (0.7 mg), Mn (1.9 mg), Zn (2.6 mg), and Cr (0.2 mg). The use of different cultivars and processing techniques for the okara from soybeans may account for the compositional difference. Okara is highly prone to decay and decomposition due to its high nutritional quality and high water activity. Hence, the functionality of the okara protein and the pretreatment of okara to improve protein extraction efficiency will be the main topics of this review.

Okara Protein

Okara is a soybean curd residue with high protein quality and a superior protein efficiency ratio. It can be used as a cheap and readily available source of vegetable protein for human consumption. The extraction method, environment, and cultivar of the soybean all affect how much protein is present. Ma *et al.* (1997) isolated the protein from okara, which was less soluble in acidic and alkaline pH than Supro 610. It also had functional properties similar to commercial Supro 610, such as emulsifying, water and fat binding, and foaming.

Figure 1: Flow chart of the okara manufacturing process (Vong & Liu, 2016; Guimaraes *et al.*, 2018, Kamble and Rani 2020).

Okara protein contains 7S globulin and 11S globulin, which are two major protein fractions in Okara. It also contains essential amino acids such as cysteine and methionine. De Figueiredo *et al.* (2018) and Liu *et al.* (2017) reported that glycinin (11S globulin) has a molecular weight of 36-40 kDa and 18-20 kDa, respectively. Okara (dry basis) comprises 15.2-33.4% protein, and the major protein constituents are 7S globulin and 11S globulin. Okara protein has an estimated protein efficiency ratio of 2.71, making it a higher-quality protein than other soy products. However, its low solubility in water is a problem for extraction. Chan and Ma (1999) investigated the solubility of the okara subjected to acid treatment and found that both the solubility and functional properties had significantly increased.

Soybean Protein

The amount of protein in okara is directly correlated with the quality of the protein in soybeans. Globulins are the primary proteins stored in soybean (Wolf *et al.*, 1992). Stanojevic *et al.* (2010) divided the sedimentation fractions into four groups: 2S, 7S, 11S, and 15S. They described the various types of protein in soybeans based on the coefficient of sedimentation following centrifugation in standard phosphate buffer. They added that 7S and 11S make up more than 70% of the soluble proteins in soybeans. 7S fractions make up about 67% of the total protein in soybeans. Lecitins, basic 7S-globulin, β -conglycinin, γ -conglycinin, and small amounts of the enzymes lipoxygenase and β -amylase make up most of the 7S proteins found in soybeans. However, 90% of the entire 7S fraction is made up of β -Conglycinin (7 S-globulin, vicilin) as the main protein. It accounts for 30% of all soybean proteins and 16.8–20% of soluble proteins. Glycinin (11S-globulin, legumin), regarded as one of the major constituents of protein among the fractions of 11S, makes up about 32% of the total proteins in soybeans. Glycinin is found in two main zones during SDS-PAGE analysis, one from the monomer and the other from the dimer (Stanojevic *et al.*, 2010).

Amino Acid Profile of Okara Protein

The amino acids in okara protein include both essential and non-essential amino acids. De Figueiredo *et al.* (2018) analyzed the amino acid profile in grams per 100 grams of the protein concentrate to determine both essential and non-essential amino acids. The total essential amino acid content was 36.97 g/g. Proline predominates the amino acid profile, with 44.4% of the amino acids being hydrophobic and 33% being hydrophilic. The low solubility of okara protein may be due to the high proportion of hydrophobic amino acids.

Commercial Utilization of Okara Protein

According to the literature, there are two main ways to incorporate okara into foods. The entire okara can be used as a component in finished goods. Second, several components isolated from the okara can be used as ingredients (Colleti *et al.*, 2020).

Okara protein hydrolysis for peptide production

Okara protein hydrolysates can be used to recover valuable peptides from nutrients that are discarded in okara. Enzymatic hydrolysis increases the antioxidant activity of peptides by exposing antioxidant amino acids in proteins. Protein hydrolysates are excellent sources of low molecular weight peptides and have high digestibility.

As a non-meat protein source for making meat burgers

Okara can be used as a non-meat protein source to make reduced-fat beef burgers without affecting the products' sensory quality (Su *et al.*, 2013). According to a study by Su *et al.* (2013), there was more protein in beef burgers with added okara (16 g/100 g) than in commercial beef burgers (14 g). The same report also noted that beef burger with added okara had a calorific value of about 106 kcal/100 g, which was less than commercial burger, which had a calorific value of 269 kcal/100 g. This demonstrates the superior nutritional benefits of using okara as a source of protein in burgers.

Okara protein in the production of nutritional foods

Okara is a wholesome food by-product, so it is valued for creating wholesome foods. Many nations, including Japan and the United States, place great importance on the reuse of okara (Li *et al.*, 2013). According to Colletti *et al.* (2020), Figure 2 depicts typical soybean by-products. In the production of foods like bread, pancakes, puff pastries, pasta sausages, and nutritional flour, to increase the foods' protein and fibre content, okara can be used in place of soybean flour

and wheat flour (Colletti *et al.*, 2010). Sudal *et al.* (2007) created bread and pancakes by mixing okara powder, which contains about 21% vegetable protein, about 50% dietary fibre, and 0.45% calcium.

Figure 2: Soybeans byproduct production (Colletti *et al.*, 2020).

Animal feeds

Okara is an excellent alternative source of organic protein for young pigs, as it contains high levels of protein and non-fibrous carbohydrates. It is less expensive than soybean meal and can be used as a partial replacement for common feeds.

Functional Properties of Okara Protein/Soybean Protein

Okara proteins' structural variations affect their functionality when added to food production systems, as they interact with external factors such as temperature, pH, and ionic strength.

Solubility

Solubility of protein is affected by the amount of protein in a solvent, which is important for food applications. Okara protein's low solubility at alkaline pH is due to aggregations of proteins, while soy protein is highest at all pH levels.

Water-holding capacity

Okara protein has a water-holding capacity of 4.3 ml/g compared to commercial soybean protein isolate Supro 610. Enzymatic hydrolysis and membrane filtration can increase water-holding capacity, but not fat-binding capacity.

Oil-binding capacity

Okara protein has a higher fat-holding capacity than Supro 610, and its ability to bind fat changes during deamination, possibly due to its bulk density.

Emulsification properties

Beta-conglycinin forms a more stable emulsion than glycinin due to its lower molecular weight and hydrophobicity, and its emulsifying ability and emulsion stability are higher than those of glycinin. The rate of adsorption at

the interphase and the amount of protein determine the emulsifying property of soy protein ingredients. Acid modifications have improved the emulsifying property of Okara protein, but the emulsifying stability index is unaffected.

Foaming properties

Foaming properties are essential for certain food applications, such as ice cream, whipped cream, bread, cakes, cereal-based products, meringues, chocolate bars, marshmallows, champagne and beer. Okara protein isolate (OPI) exhibited higher foaming stability than Supro 610 due to its high net charge density. Enzymatic hydrolysis of okara protein did not improve foaming properties. Rice protein concentrates showed good foaming stability of 42.6 h half-life at 15% sugar concentration. Bran rice protein has a good foaming capacity comparable to egg white.

Extraction of the Protein from Okara

Traditional extraction methods for extracting okara from soybean result in a negligible reduction in oligosaccharides, but may still contain phytic acid and insoluble carbohydrates.

Aqueous alkaline extraction

The main protein in soybeans, globulins, is typically extracted using this method. Defatted okara flour is dissolved in water and pH adjusted to an alkaline solution. The protein is then precipitated at a lower pH and re-dispersed in water with a pH of 7. The solubilized protein is either freeze-dried or spray-dried to produce the okara protein isolate. Vishwanathan et al. (2011) used three stages of protein extraction to recover 87% and 80% of the proteins from okara. However, the extraction temperature was close to or above 68°C and 82°C, which could denature the two significant proteins from soybeans.

Enzyme – assisted extraction

The enzyme-assisted extraction method of proteins is time-consuming and costly, requiring enzyme concentrations of >1%. Several researchers have investigated the extraction of okara protein from soybean meal using enzymes. Sarra *et al.* (2016) found that soybean meal had a higher potential for protein extraction than Fischer *et al.* (2001). Okara contains much insoluble fibre, making it challenging for enzymes to digest (Kasai *et al.*, 2004). Therefore, the digestion process would need to include several steps, such as autoclaving for 20 min at 121°C to obtain about 83-85% w/w protein yield. This will be followed by cellulase digestion using 1% enzyme at 40°C for 15 h to digest the cell wall and pectinase (Cassab, 1998).

Membrane filtration technology

Membrane technology can be used to recover okara protein, increasing its value and comparing the functional characteristics of okara protein concentrate (MOPC), membrane soy protein concentrate (MSPC), and commercial protein. Vishwanathan et al. (2011) used a two-step sequential extraction methodology with a w/v ratio of 1:10 and 1:20 to recover 80% of okara and 90% of soy protein.

Ultrasonication-assisted extraction

Ultrasound is a mechanical vibration that travels through objects at frequencies higher than those audible to humans. It causes localised cavitation, which fragments particles or cells and enables faster extraction rates. Ultrasonication has been used to enhance the extraction of plant constituents, such as phenolic compounds from coconut shell powder and hesperidin from pengan's peel. It causes localised temperatures and pressures to produce free radicals, which can change the native conformation structure of proteins, enhancing their functional properties. Ultrasound-assisted enzymatic extraction has been used to extract polysaccharides from pumpkin, soybean flakes, and okara protein, with a high recovery

of protein with an effect on functional activities. This may reduce protein's ability to emulsify, maintain foaming stability, and have rheological properties.

Pretreatment of Okara to Increase Protein Extraction Efficiency

Pre-treatment methods have been used to increase the effectiveness of okara protein, divided into chemical, physical, and enzymatic categories.

Chemical method of pre-treatment

Chemical methods of pretreatment of okara protein (OP) include alkaline hydrolysis and late precipitation at lower pH. Different pH ranges, both acidic and alkaline, are employed to reduce or stop protein degradation. A phosphate buffer of pH 7.4 was used for extraction of glycosylated protein. Nguyen *et al.* (2016) used an aqueous extraction method to extract the protein from the supernatant. Campbell & Mougeot (2000) and Kinsella *et al.* (1979) reported that the majority of soy proteins have their solubility at pH 3 and >6. Chamba *et al.* (2013) found that SPI produced using natural chemicals showed more emulsion stability, emulsion capacity, oil absorption and foam stability, and lower antioxidants.

Physical treatment

In order to disrupt plant tissue and increase protein yield during the extraction process, a number of physical pre-treatment techniques have been used. These techniques include thermal (heat treatment), ultrasonic, steam cooking, homogenization, and microwave.

Thermal processing pre-treatment

Heat treatment of okara and soy proteins can affect their solubility and emulsifying properties, but pretreated SPI has superior emulsification and fat-binding properties than untreated SPI from white flake. Proteins should be extracted below 70°C to improve yield and inactivate LOX and trypsin inhibitors, but it is important to weigh the loss of protein components against the improvement in solubility. The extraction of okara protein was more sensitive to temperature than soy flour, and when the temperature was raised from 25 to 90°C, the protein yield and functional properties were improved.

Homogenization pre-treatment

Non-convective technologies can be used to regulate plant-based materials' functional properties. High-pressure homogenization (HPH) is a favourable technology that can induce cell disruption, particle size reduction, and modification of macromolecules. Despite mechanical strains, turbulence cavitation and impact with the solid surface can occur at the valve outlet. Okara dispersion using HPH can present benefits such as protein and fibrous materials extraction, biopolymer structure modification, and the development of novel particle interactions and networking. However, homogenization can cause a negative effect on separation efficiency. Fayaz *et al.* (2019) recorded an improvement in the extraction and yield of okara protein from soy okara dispersion after homogenization at 100MPa for 1 pass. Homogenization to 100MPa and 150MPa leads to the progressive reduction of dimension, number of crystallization particles, and the number of particles that may occur due to the solubility.

Pretreatment by ultrasonic method

Tao *et al.* (2019) extracted okara protein using (homogenisation pretreatment), UPAT (Ultrasonic pretreatment) and SPAT (steam-cooking). Results showed that homogenisation and ultrasonic decreased the hydrophobicity of the protein significantly, while steam-cooking pretreatment significantly increased the hydrophobicity. Pretreatment methods can affect solubility. Ultrasonic pretreatment of okara protein has been found to significantly increase the stability of emulsions, but

has lower foaming ability than the soy protein isolate. Preece *et al.* (2017) reported that ultrasound pretreatment of soy slurry and okara at 20kHz, in 1min at 50°C, improved extraction yields of proteins by 11% and 14%. Fan *et al.* (2021) examined the impact of high-intensity ultrasound treatment on the physicochemical properties, gelation process, water-holding capacity and microstructures of okara tofu analogues. Results showed a decrease in the particle size, but the surface hydrophobicity and sulfhydryl group of the content increased.

Enzyme assisted pretreatment of okara protein

Enzyme pretreatment helps improve protein extraction and yield by reducing cell wall rigidity. Kasai *et al.* (2003, 2004) reported that cellulase hydrolyses the primary cell wall, but pectinase only hydrolyses the secondary cell wall. Viscozyme was used to extract protein from okara at 37-53°C and pH 5.5-6.5. Enzyme-assisted subcritical water treatment improved protein extraction and yield by 59.3%.

Microwave pretreatment

Microwave technology can increase protein yield, improve gel strength, storage modulus, and water-holding capacity of soybean protein isolate, and reduce allergenicity by 24.7, 18.9%, 46.6%, and 29.8%.

Conclusion

Okara protein is extracted by grinding soybeans, extracting intracellular components, and separating the waste product. Different pre-treatment techniques are used to understand the differences in properties. The availability of okara protein is influenced by factors such as temperature, pH, and ionic strength. HPH was found to be more effective in extracting and recovering protein with better functionalities. Steam cooking preserves the stability of the foam, but enzymes and microwave heating produce proteins with a good yield. Ultrasound may be an excellent method to consider. In conclusion, managing various okara pre-treatments can affect the protein's extractability and specific functionalities, including solubility, foaming stability, water-holding capacity, and emulsification ability.

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